

ADVANCED BIOCOMPOSITES MADE FROM METHACRYLATED EPOXIDIZED SUCROSE SOYATE RESIN REINFORCED WITH FLAX FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Flax fiber composites were processed with a liquid molding Methacrylated Epoxidized Sucrose Soyate (MESS) resin in order to compare the mechanical performance of composites containing the MESS to those containing a commonly used synthetic based Vinyl Ester (VE). Fiber treatments carried out with different mechanical cleaning steps were also investigated in order to determine their effect on fiber/matrix adhesion and composite performance. Flax fibers were impregnated using a hand lay-up compression molding process achieving composites with fiber volume fractions ranging from 30%-39%. Composite mechanical performance was characterized by performing tensile, flexure, and short beam shear tests. Using untreated flax fibers, composites made from either MESS or VE resins exhibited improvements in tensile and flexural modulus when compared to composites made from mechanically treated flax fibers. However, composites made from flax fibers mechanically treated to improve fibril separation and removal of residual pectin and waxes exhibited improved tensile, flexural, and interlaminar shear strength when compared to untreated flax fiber composites. Composites made from MESS resin exhibited improved wetting of both the untreated and mechanically treated flax fiber surface and improved consolidation of the composite as shown by micro-tomography (i.e. micro CT).

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermosetting polymers such as unsaturated polyester, epoxy, vinyl ester and phenol-formaldehyde resins have been widely used in the modern composites industry because of their low density, good mechanical properties, low cost, dimensional stability and high corrosion resistance. Traditionally, these resins have been synthesized using petroleum-based chemicals as the raw materials. The replacement of the petroleum-based polymers with their bio-based counterparts is a recent innovation in the field of “green composites” [1, 2]. Some economic advantages of using bio-based polymers include global accessibility and relatively low cost. Additionally, plant oils are one of the most important bio-renewable chemical feed stocks for the polymer industry because of their high annual production, high availability, low toxicity, relatively low cost, and biodegradability. However, the development of bio-based resins for structural composites applications is still a challenge for the polymer and composite industries [3-6].

In addition, natural fibers have a great potential to be used as reinforcement in composite materials [7]. Cellulose being a critical constituent of natural fibers provides us with unquestionable advantages

over glass fiber [8]. Lower density, higher toughness and comparable strength and stiffness, lower cost, and being biodegradable and renewable are some of advantages of natural fibers compared to glass fiber or other synthetic or mineral fibers. On the other hand, natural fibers have a high tendency of moisture absorption which can cause problems in some applications [7]. Therefore, increasing and modifying the adhesion between the fiber and matrix has been subject of many studies [7, 9-11]. In general, tensile strength as well as young's modulus of natural fibers are lower than that of glass fiber. Comparing the density of glass fiber (2.5 g/m^3) with that of natural fibers ($\sim 1.4\text{-}1.5 \text{ g/m}^3$) it is observed that specific strength and specific modulus of some of natural fibers are comparable to glass fiber [12, 13]. Some common natural fibers used as reinforcement in composite materials are flax, hemp, kenaf, sisal, henequen and jute. Physical properties of natural fibers are related to internal structure and composition of the fiber [14].

Flax fiber are commonly composed of 70-80% cellulose, during the biological synthesis of plant cell, cellulose and hemicellulose fibers are produced and lignin fills the spaces between polysaccharide [13]. There are also other non-cellulosic elements present in structure of flax such as pectin, protein or mineral substances, tannins and dyes. High content of non-cellulosic substances in the flax fiber is not desirable since they will have a negative influence on spinning, weaving, bonding and finishing processes [14]. Figure 1 shows a typical cross-section of flax fiber used in this study obtained by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

Figure 1. Scanning Electron Microscopy image of cross-section of flax fiber used in this study.

The mechanical and cleaning process of flax fiber prior to use as reinforcement in composite materials as well as increasing and modifying the adhesion between fiber and matrix has been subject of many studies [7, 9, 14-17]. A thorough understanding of different mechanical and cleaning processes of natural fibers is valuable in development of their applications [18], since they can target a specific mechanical property to be improved by use of a certain mechanical process.

In this study, a novel high-functional bio-based resin from Methacrylated Epoxidized Sucrose Soyate (MESS) was used as a matrix. The mechanical properties of fibers with different mechanical treatments using novel MESS thermoset resin were compared with composites using Vinyl Ester (VE) as their thermoset resin.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Two types of resins, bio-based and petroleum-based and one type of fiber reinforcement were used in this study. Fiber was linen flax, farmed and harvested by the University of Saskatchewan, Saskatoon province, Canada, received in the form of fiber roving. Shive (i.e. woody core of the flax stalk) was removed by passing the fiber through pilot line eight times. Three different mechanical processes were carried out and each type of fiber is described as follows (Type 1 through Type 4):

- Type 1 (untreated): No further mechanical process was performed on fiber.
Type 2 (opener treatment): Fiber was combed ten times by “opener” machine in a rough manner.
Type 3 (blend of over retted): A 50/50 blend of optimally retted fiber and over retted fiber. Fiber was also carded once.
Type 4 (fluted roller treatment): Fiber was passed through a pair of small fluted rollers ten times to remove remaining shive.

The bio-based resin used in this study was produced at the Department of Coatings and Polymeric Materials of North Dakota State University. Methacrylated Epoxidized Sucrose Soyate (MESS) resin was made by the reaction of Epoxidized Sucrose Soyate (ESS) and Methacrylic Acid. ESS was synthesized from fully esterified sucrose soyate as reported previously in [19, 20]. The MESS resin was too viscous to be used for thermoset formulations. Therefore, styrene was introduced as a reactive diluent to reduce the viscosity, as well as a co-monomer to increase the rigidity of the resulting thermoset. The resulting resin contained 30% styrene. The resin was mixed with tert-butyl peroxybenzoate 98% (Luperox® P) as a high temperature initiator, cumyl hydroperoxide 45% (Trigonox 239A) as a room temperature initiator, and cobalt naphthenate (CoNap) as a promoter. The mixing ratio of Luperox® P, Trigonox 239A and CoNap were 2, 3, and 1 wt%, respectively. Styrene, Luperox® P and cobalt naphthenate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co. located in St. Louis, Missouri, USA. Cumyl Peroxide commercially available as Trigonox 239A, was generously provided by AkzoNobel Co. Located in Amsterdam, Netherlands. The second resin was a vinyl ester (VE) system Hydropel® R037-YDF-40, generously provided by AOC resins Co. located in Collierville, Tennessee, USA. The hardener for VE resin was a 2-butanone peroxide (Luperox® DDM-9) solution, which was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Co. St. Louis, Missouri, USA. Mixing ration of VE and hardener was 100 to 1 weight parts.

2.2 Processing the Composite Panels

To manufacture the composite panels, fiber roving was processed with a manual drum carder machine model DC-P05-B/A from Strauch Fiber Equipment Co. located in New Castle, Virginia, USA, shown in Figure 2. For each composite panel 50±4 g of fiber was run through carder machine once with total of 500 revolutions of drum.

Figure 2. a) Carder machine used in this study and b) flax fiber before and after carding process.

Composite panels were manufactured using a hand-layup compression molding process. As mentioned, for each plate 50 ± 4 g of fiber was placed in the mold and 250 g of resin was poured onto the fiber till the fiber was soaked in resin. A nonporous PTFE sheet was placed on top of the fiber and a caul plate with dimensions of 200 mm by 150 mm was placed on top of the fiber. Everything was sealed under a layer of vacuum bagging plastic and five metric tons of force was applied by a shop press. The applied force will result in 1.6 MPa pressure over the fiber. A schematic of the composite plate manufacturing layup is shown in Figure 3. All composite plates using VE resin were under pressure for 24 hours at room temperature and then post cured at 80 °C for 12 hours. The panels using MESS resin were under pressure for 12 hours at 23.8 °C, one hours at 150 °C, one hour at 175 °C and two hours at 200 °C. To avoid warpage, the panels were cooled down to room temperature under pressure. The resulting composite plates had average thickness of 3 mm. All samples were kept in the oven at 80 °C prior to testing.

Figure 3. Composite panel manufacturing layup.

2.3 Characterization Methods

2.3.1 Short beam shear test

Interlaminar properties were evaluated by means of short beam strength test in accordance with ASTM D2344 using an Instron 5567 load frame. Five samples were tested for each plate in displacement controlled mode with rate of displacement of cross-head set to 1 mm/min.

2.3.2 Flexural test

Three-point bending tests were performed on five samples from each plate in accordance with ASTM D790. Maximum flexural stress and flexural modulus were calculated based on ASTM D790 [21].

2.3.3 Tensile test

From each panel, five tensile test specimens were prepared according to ASTM standard D3039. An Instron 5567 load frame was used to perform tensile tests on composite samples. Ultimate tensile strength and modulus of elasticity was calculated from results of these tensile tests in accordance with ASTM standard D3039 [22].

2.3.4 Density test

To determine fiber densities, flax fiber samples were tested at Composite Innovation Center (CIC) in Manitoba province, Canada. The method used was Pycnometry using dry Nitrogen gas purge with 17 psig pressure.

Density of composite panels and cured resins were measured using a Mettler Toledo 33360 density determination kit. Minimum of five samples from each composite plate were weighted both in the air and submerged in distilled water with density of 0.9975 g/cm^3 at 23.5 °C. The density was calculated from the following equation:

$$\rho_s = \frac{W_a}{W_a - W_w} \times \rho_w \quad (1)$$

Where ρ_s is the specimen's density (g/cm^3), W_a is the weight of specimen in the air (g), W_w is the weight of specimen submerged in water (g) and ρ_w is the density of distilled water (g/cm^3).

2.3.5 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images of treated and untreated flax fiber were captured using a JEOL JSM-6490LV scanning electron microscope at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV.

2.3.6 Micro-Computed Tomography (micro-CT)

In order to visually and internally evaluate fiber matrix interaction and quality of manufactured plates, 3D micro-Ct scans were acquired using a General Electric 240 kV micro-focus X-ray computed tomography system (v|tome|x micro-CT).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of density measurements and fiber volume fraction of composite plates are presented in Table 1. To minimize the effect of variations in fiber volume fraction in different composite plates on mechanical properties, all calculated mechanical properties were normalized to 35% fiber volume fraction.

Flax Fiber	$\rho_{fiber} (\text{g/cm}^3)$	Resin	$\rho_{resin} (\text{g/cm}^3)$	$\rho_{composite} (\text{g/cm}^3)$	$V_f (\%)$
Type 1	1.52 ± 0.001	VE	1.09 ± 0.003	1.23 ± 0.006	35.50
		MESS	1.15 ± 0.002	1.10 ± 0.024	31.43
Type 2	1.54 ± 0.000	VE	1.09 ± 0.003	1.25 ± 0.032	39.12
		MESS	1.15 ± 0.002	1.11 ± 0.020	33.44
Type 3	1.55 ± 0.000	VE	1.09 ± 0.003	1.22 ± 0.020	37.84
		MESS	1.15 ± 0.002	1.10 ± 0.017	30.10
Type 4	1.54 ± 0.000	VE	1.09 ± 0.003	1.25 ± 0.051	36.60
		MESS	1.15 ± 0.002	1.13 ± 0.024	34.47

Table 1. Density of fibers, resins, composite panels and fiber volume fraction of manufactured panels.

Figure 4 shows SEM images of untreated and mechanically treated fibers. It is observed that mechanical processes were successful to some extent in removal of waxes and pectin from surface of the fibers. As seen, Type 2 and Type 4 fibers show cleaner surfaces compared to Type 1 (untreated). On the other hand, in Type 3, both clean fibers are seen as well as fibers covered in waxes and impurities. One interesting observation seen in SEM images of Type 4 fiber is twisting and entanglement of single fibers and formation of micro-bundles of fibers. The mechanical process used on these type of fiber was use of a pair of fluted rollers. Use of fluted rollers also resulted in less shive content compared to other types of fibers.

A typical 3D micro-CT image is shown in Figure 5. As mentioned before, micro-CT can reveal any manufacturing flaws in the specimen. Also, it can be used in conjunction with image processing software to calculate void content of composite panels.

As result of mentioned tests, tensile strength, tensile modulus, flexural strength, flexural modulus and shear strength was calculated. Normalized average of measured values are presented in Table 2. Also, a radar plot of measured mechanical properties of flax / VE resin is shown in Figure 6 and flax / MESS resin is shown in Figure 7. It is worth mentioning that the purpose of Figure 6 and Figure 7 is to qualitatively compare mechanical properties. Because of the differences in the orders of magnitude of different properties, values have been scaled up or down to show a side by side comparison.

Based on the results seen in Table 2, resulting composite panel from fiber Type 3 which contains 50/50 blend of over retted fibers and optimally retted fibers, showed lower mechanical properties compared to other three composite panels. This difference is more noticeable in flexural modulus where the average measured value for flexural modulus is 6.01 GPa for flax/VE composite samples, the lowest of all measurements. The same trend is observed for flax Type 3/ MESS resin where all the mechanical properties are lower than other three types of fibers. The fiber used to manufacture this composite panel was from straw that was over retted. This resulted in weaker, shorter and finer diameter fiber. Although it is blended 50/50 with optimally retted fiber, still the mechanical properties of resulting composite are inferior to that of others.

For tensile and flexural strength, fiber Type 4 showed comparable properties to untreated/VE composites and better strength compared to untreated/MESS composites and other types of fibers using MESS resin. This can be attributed to two factors, first, lower shive content of fiber, as shive has lower strength compared to flax fiber [23] and second, twisting of fibers and formations of micro-bundles as seen in SEM images. In composites using flax fiber reinforcement with VE resin, untreated fibers showed higher strength than Type 2 fibers while composites using MESS resin Type 2 fiber showed better strength.

Figure 4. SEM images of flax fiber using four different mechanical processes.

Moreover, it is observed that Type 2 fibers both with VE and MESS resins showed 5% improvement in shear strength compared to untreated fiber and 20% increase compared to Type 4 treatment.

Tensile and flexural modulus of composites were decreased with additional fiber mechanical processes. In other word, for both VE and MESS resins, untreated fibers exhibited higher flexural and tensile modulus. Comparing the overall results of two types of resins, composites using MESS resin possess higher tensile and flexural modulus. On the other hand, they showed lower tensile, flexural and interlaminar shear strength. This can be the result of higher curing temperature used for MESS resin. As reported by Vold et al. [24], flax shive starts to degrade between 225 °C and 250 °C. Composite panels using MESS resin were cured at 200 °C for two hours, and this can be the reason for lower strength of mentioned composites due to start of degradation of shive content of the fiber.

	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Interlaminar Shear Strength (MPa)
Type1 – VE	108.08 ± 2.27	15.43 ± 0.45	124.77 ± 3.15	9.30 ± 0.08	12.39 ± 0.70
Type1 - MESS	27.82 ± 1.61	17.06 ± 1.67	41.83 ± 1.46	15.04 ± 0.44	7.97 ± 2.66
Type2 – VE	93.92 ± 3.26	12.87 ± 0.45	114.93 ± 5.54	8.85 ± 0.71	13.06 ± 0.74
Type2 - MESS	42.01 ± 4.69	14.30 ± 0.41	61.92 ± 6.83	14.71 ± 1.70	9.16 ± 1.34
Type3 – VE	81.40 ± 2.67	12.59 ± 0.87	103.61 ± 2.44	6.01 ± 0.34	10.06 ± 0.46
Type3 - MESS	26.30 ± 5.61	12.87 ± 1.26	35.43 ± 5.97	9.59 ± 0.55	4.28 ± 0.67
Type4 – VE	104.95 ± 3.85	14.03 ± 1.00	131.96 ± 3.37	8.51 ± 1.13	10.82 ± 0.69
Type4 - MESS	49.57 ± 5.78	16.41 ± 2.55	64.97 ± 2.63	12.85 ± 1.60	7.03 ± 0.68

Table 2. Normalized mechanical properties of flax/VE and flax/MESS composites.

Figure 5. A typical micro-CT of specimen from manufactured composite panels.

Figure 6. Mechanical Properties of flax/VE composites using four different types of flax fiber.

Figure 7. Mechanical Properties of flax/MESS composites using four different types of flax fiber.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, a novel highly-functional bio-based resin from Methacrylated Epoxidized Sucrose Soyate (MESS) was used as the matrix. The mechanical properties of fibers with different mechanical treatments using novel MESS thermoset resin were compared with composites using Vinyl Ester (VE) as their thermoset resin. Untreated flax fiber and three mechanical cleaning and processes were used to clean the fibers prior to use as reinforcement in the composites. Composite mechanical performance was characterized by performing tensile, flexure, and short beam shear tests. Untreated flax fibers, composites made from either MESS or VE resins exhibited improvements in tensile and flexural modulus when compared to composites made from mechanically treated flax fibers. Composites made from fibers treated with fluted rollers exhibited improved tensile, flexural, and inter-laminar shear strength when compared to untreated flax fiber composites and other mechanically treated fibers. However, composites made with MESS resin exhibited lower strengths compared to composites made with VE resin. This could be attributed to curing the resin at higher temperature which results in degradation of shive content of the fiber. Further study with different type of flax fiber with minimum to no shive content is required to confirm this conclusion.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. J. John and S. Thomas, "Biofibres and biocomposites," vol. 71, pp. 343-364, 2008.
- [2] H.-y. Cheung, M.-p. Ho, K.-t. Lau, F. Cardona, and D. Hui, "Natural fibre-reinforced composites for bioengineering and environmental engineering applications," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, vol. 40, pp. 655-663, 10// 2009.
- [3] M. N. Belgacem and A. Gandini, *Monomers, polymers and composites from renewable resources*, Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2011
- [4] R. P. Wool and X. S. Sun, *Bio-based Polymers and Composites*. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2005.
- [5] M. N. Belgacem and A. Gandini, *Monomers, Polymers and Composites from Renewable Resources*. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2008.
- [6] J. M. Raquez, M. Deléglise, M. F. Lacrampe, and P. Krawczak, "Thermosetting (bio)materials derived from renewable resources: A critical review," *Progress in Polymer Science*, vol. 35, pp. 487-509, 4// 2010.
- [7] B. Wang, L. Tabil, and S. Panigrahi, "Effects of chemical treatments on mechanical and physical properties of flax fiber-reinforced composites," *Science and Engineering of Composite Materials*, vol. 15, pp. 43-58, 2008.
- [8] N. Zafeiropoulos, D. Williams, C. Baillie, and F. Matthews, "Engineering and characterisation of the interface in flax fibre/polypropylene composite materials. Part I. Development and investigation of surface treatments," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 33, pp. 1083-1093, 2002.
- [9] B. Wang, S. Panigrahi, L. Tabil, and W. Crerar, "Effects of Chemical Treatments on Mechanical and Physical Properties of Flax Fiber-reinforced Rotationally Molded Composites," in *ASAE Annual Meeting, Paper*, 2004.
- [10] S. Huo, "The physico-chemical investigation of interfacial properties in natural fiber/vinyl ester biocomposites," NORTH DAKOTA STATE UNIVERSITY, 2012.

- [11] S. Huo, C. A. Ulven, H. Wang, and X. Wang, "Chemical and Mechanical Properties Studies of Chinese Linen Flax and its Composites," *Polymers & polymer composites*, vol. 21, pp. 275-285, 2013.
- [12] A. K. Mohanty, M. Misra, and L. T. Drzal, "Sustainable bio-composites from renewable resources: opportunities and challenges in the green materials world," *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, vol. 10, pp. 19-26, 2002.
- [13] X. Mo, D. Wang, and X. Sun, "Natural fibers, biopolymers, and biocomposites," *CRC: New York*, 2005.
- [14] A. Mustata, "Factors influencing fiber-fiber friction in the case of bleached flax," *Cellulose chemistry and technology*, vol. 31, pp. 405-413, 1997.
- [15] R. Joffe, J. Andersons, and L. Wallström, "Strength and adhesion characteristics of elementary flax fibres with different surface treatments," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 34, pp. 603-612, 2003.
- [16] T. Stuart, Q. Liu, M. Hughes, R. McCall, H. Sharma, and A. Norton, "Structural biocomposites from flax—Part I: Effect of bio-technical fibre modification on composite properties," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 37, pp. 393-404, 2006.
- [17] B. Wang, S. Panigrahi, L. Tabil, W. Crerar, S. Sokansanj, and L. Braun, "Modification of flax fibers by chemical treatment," in *Proceeding CSAE/SCGR Meeting, July, 2003*, pp. 6-9.
- [18] A. Amiri and C. Ulven, "Surface Treatment of Flax Fiber," presented at the 65th Flax Institute of the United States, Fargo, ND, 2014.
- [19] J. Yan and D. C. Webster. (2014, Thermosets from highly functional methacrylated epoxidized sucrose soyate. *Green Materials* 2, 132-143.
- [20] X. Pan, P. Sengupta, and D. C. Webster, "Novel biobased epoxy compounds: epoxidized sucrose esters of fatty acids," *Green Chemistry*, vol. 13, pp. 965-975, 2011.
- [21] ASTM D 790-03: "Standard Test Methods for Flexural Properties of Unreinforced and Reinforced Plastic and Electrical Insulating Materials," ASTM International West Conshohocken, PA, 2004.
- [22] ASTM D 3039M-00: "Standard test method for tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials", ASTM International West Conshohocken, PA , 2000
- [23] W. Hu, M. Zhang, M.-T. Ton-That, and T.-d. Ngo, "A comparison of flax shive and extracted flax shive reinforced PP composites," *Fibers and Polymers*, vol. 15, pp. 1722-1728, 2014.
- [24] J. L. Vold, C. A. Ulven, and B. J. Chisholm, "Torrefied biomass filled polyamide biocomposites: mechanical and physical property analysis," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 50, pp. 725-732, 2015.